

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF WATER ABSORPTION IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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SUMMARY: The objective of the present work is to study the statistical characteristics of data obtained on the moisture absorption process of composite materials. For this purpose, the glass/epoxy composite specimens were immersed in distilled water at a temperature of 46°C and the moisture content of specimen was measured in function of time. The analytical results indicated that the statistical distributions of the moisture content closely approximated the normal distribution on the nearly whole absorption process. Based on this, the statistical law of the moisture content was described and a reliability curve of water absorption was given which may be practically employed for the moisture absorption process of glass/epoxy laminated composites.

KEYWORDS: water absorption, moisture content, statistical analysis, normal distribution

INTRODUCTION

Hygrothermal environments have evident effects on the mechanical properties of composite materials. For this reason, moisture absorption has received much attention since the beginning of use of composites in structural applications. However, there is often a considerable spread in the reported results obtained on the moisture absorption process. Twenty or thirty percent variations in the data are quite common. In some cases, the results obtained by different laboratories even differ by forty percent or more^[1, 2]. This fact leads to great loss of confidence of potential users in published data.

In this paper, a statistical technique was used to study the statistical characteristics of these measured moisture parameters and the conclusions obtained here should be useful to the researchers and engineers in the field.

EXPERIMENT

All tests were performed on 8 ply glass/epoxy specimens having the following laminated types a) $[0^\circ]_8$, b) $[90^\circ]_8$, c) $[\pm 45^\circ]_{2s}$ and d) $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ]_s$. The nominal dimensions were: thickness $h = 2.00$ mm, width $b = 15.00$ mm and length $l = 150.00$ mm. The fiber volume fraction was about 60 percent for all specimens.

The specimens were primarily dried in a dry environment chamber until no more weight losses were observed. The dry specimens were then immersed in distilled water at a constant temperature about 46°C. The weight changes of specimens were measured by weighing them periodically on a mettler analytical balance with an accuracy of 0.001g.

CLASSICAL LAW AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Fick's Law

It has been demonstrated that under most conditions the moisture content of composites such as glass/epoxy may be calculated using the equivalent unidirectional Fick's law^[1], namely:

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 c}{\partial x^2} \quad (1)$$

where c is the moisture concentration at time t at a point a distance x from the surface and D is the moisture diffusivity.

Using the Equation (1), we obtain the moisture content of the specimens studied :

$$M = M_m \left(1 - \frac{8}{\pi^2} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{\exp \left[-(2j+1)^2 \pi^2 \left(\frac{Dt}{h^2} \right) \right]}{(2j+1)^2} \right) \quad (2)$$

According to Shen and Springer^[1], Equation (2) may be approximated by :

$$M = M_m \left(1 - \exp \left[-7.3 \left(\frac{Dt}{h^2} \right)^{0.75} \right] \right) \quad (3)$$

where M_m is the maximum moisture content and t is the immersion time.

In fact, the water also enters the specimen through the "edges"(surfaces h_l and h_b), so D in Equation (2) and (3) should be considered as a equivalent diffusivity , it can be expressed as^[1]:

$$D = D_x \left(1 + \frac{h}{l} \sqrt{\frac{D_y}{D_x}} + \frac{h}{b} \sqrt{\frac{D_z}{D_x}} \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

where D_x , D_y , D_z are the diffusivity respectively along the direction of thickness h , length l , and width b of the specimens.

According to Equation (4), the process of water absorption will vary with the laminated types of composites due to "Edge Effects"^[1]. But, the real cases have showed that the errors of measured data were much more important than this kind of "Edge Effects", so that, the calculated results by Equation (4) nearly lost their practical significances^[3]. Analysing the causes, we think the Equation (4) is only a mathematical diffusion model, some more important parameters were not taken into account^[3], such as the factors of manufacturing process, the inherent variation of different laminates and so on.

However, considering the considerable dispersion of data, these factors, including the variation of different laminates, may be treated as random variables in the statistical analysis.

The Moisture Content

The weight change of specimen is defined as:

$$M = \frac{\text{weight of specimen} - \text{weight of dry specimen}}{\text{weight of dry specimen}} \times 100 \text{ percent} \tag{5}$$

It should be noted that the change of weight is complex because this parameter includes weight gain due to water absorption and weight loss due to material dissolution[4,5]. However, in the early stage of the process, the weight loss is relatively small and could be neglected. Here, in order to simplify the analysis we approximately regard the total weight change M as the moisture content of material during whole absorption process studied.

So, using equation (5), we can measure M as a function of immersion time for the four different laminates ($[0^\circ]_8$, $[90^\circ]_8$, $[\pm 45^\circ]_{2s}$ and $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ]_s$). The Figure 1 presents experimental results of M obtained in function of the root of the immersion time. It is interesting to note that the data dispersion is remarkable during the whole water absorption process and face to this dispersion, it is not so significant the effect of the laminate type on the values of M. If we fit the experimental results with the Fick's law curve (Eq.3) in Figure 1, the classical Fick' law seems giving a good tendency, but it can't give any assessment of dispersion of the measured moisture parameter. Therefore we will use statistical technique to study the dispersion characteristics of M and try to give a statistical law for describing the water absorption process, where each M measured for any laminate type whatever will be considered as one event .

Figure 1: Moisture content in function of the root of the immersion time for the four laminates of glass/epoxy

STATISTICAL LAW OF WATER ABSORPTION

Test Method for Normal Distribution

As well known, the statistical advantages of the normal distribution are quite considerable and many physical measurements has been found following approximately the normal curve. The normal distribution corresponds to the following equation:

$$F(x) = \int_{-\infty}^x \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} \exp\left[-\frac{(t-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right] dt \quad (6)$$

where $F(x)$ is the cumulative probability from $-\infty$ to an assigned value x , μ is the mean of the population and σ is the standard deviation of the population.

In order to determine whether the frequency distribution of the M values for a given immersion time approximates a normal distribution, the following steps have be performed:

1. range the data of M from smallest to largest value and divide them into a series of equal-valued "class intervals", and calculate, for the class interval number i , the mean of M : M_i ;
2. determine the frequency of the data falling within class interval number i and the corresponding cumulative frequency, the last was transformed then as the standard normal variable μ_{pi} with the help of the statistical table of normal distribution;
3. The M_i values so obtained are plotted against the μ_{pi} values. If these points can be fitted well with a straight line, the normal distribution of the measured M is verified.

This method will be used for determining the statistical distribution of the moisture parameter.

Statistical Distributions of the Moisture Content

In our statistical analysis, under the same immersion time, the M measurement has been carried out on at least 21 specimens, which are grouped as a sample of population. The population, in this case, is the collection of all laminated types of composite studied which possessed the same volume fraction of the fiber and were tested under the same condition. Certainly, this treatment will provide us a statistical law in a more broad sense.

Using the method mentioned above, we have tested 15 groups of data corresponding respectively to different immersion times. The relations between M and μ_p are illustrated in Figure 2 . It is indicated that the points for each immersion time correspond well to a straight line and so we can conclude that the statistical distributions of the moisture content well approximate the Normal Distribution on the nearly whole absorption process.

Figure 2: The relations between M and μ_p

This resultant can be described as:

$$M(t) = \bar{M}(t) + \sigma(t) \mu_p \tag{7}$$

where $\bar{M}(t)$ is the mean of the population, $\sigma(t)$ is the standard deviation of the population for a given immersion time t and μ_p is the standard normal variable.

Table 1 presents the results obtained for the normal parameters $\bar{M}(t)$ and $\sigma(t)$ at each immersion time studied.

Table 1: Estimated parameters $\bar{M}(t)$ and $s(t)$ in function of the immersion time

Immersion time t (days)	Mean of the population μ (%)	Standard deviation σ (%)	Linear correlation coefficient r
4	0.184	0.0417	0.994
16	0.243	0.0472	0.984
25	0.297	0.0435	0.990
49	0.404	0.0455	0.984
64	0.462	0.0447	0.990
81	0.499	0.0449	0.993
100	0.537	0.0498	0.978
121	0.563	0.0519	0.991
144	0.596	0.0520	0.983
169	0.619	0.0480	0.987
196	0.636	0.0527	0.992
225	0.648	0.0574	0.997
256	0.665	0.0641	0.990

Correlation to Fick's Law

Based on the results of $\overline{M}(t)$ presented in Table 1, we can estimate the maximum moisture content: $M_m^\mu = 0.68\%$, and the moisture diffusivity $D^\mu = 6.251 \times 10^{-8} \text{ mm}^2/\text{sec}$. They are necessary to establish the Fick's law (Eq. 3). The figure 3 makes a comparison between the points of $\overline{M}(t)$ presented in Table 1 and the equation 3, a good correlation has been observed.

Figure 3: $\overline{M}(t)$ as a function of the root of the immersion time

Similarly, analysing the standard deviation $\sigma(t)$ obtained (Tab.1), it seems that the results of $\sigma(t)$ can be well described by an empirical model as (to see Figure 4):

$$\sigma(t) = A \exp(B\sqrt{t}) \tag{9}$$

where $A = 0,037\%$, $B = 0,0127\text{days}^{-1/2}$.

So, the statistical law of the moisture content $M(t)$ can be written as :

$$M(t) = M_m^\mu \left(1 - \exp \left[-7.3 \left(\frac{D^\mu t}{h^2} \right)^{0.75} \right] \right) + A \exp(B\sqrt{t}) \mu_p \tag{10}$$

where μ_p is the standard normal variable and the second term of the equation may be regarded as the statistical modification of classical Fick' law.

Figure 4: $\sigma(t)$ as a function of the root of the immersion time

Application — Reliability Curve of M(t)

Based on the above results, we can deal quantitatively with the dispersion of water absorption process. The reliability curve of M(t) is a valuable example.

If we define the reliability degree $R=0.90$, the values of M(t) under the cumulative probability 5% (correspond to $\mu_p = -1.645$) and 95% (correspond to $\mu_p = 1.645$) can be determined by using equation (10). Plotting the results on the figure 5, a reliability curve of M(t) is obtained. It means that for the 8 ply glass/epoxy specimens with a 65% volume fraction of the fiber under a test condition of this paper, it has 90% reliability for the M(t) to fall within the interval of 5% and 95% cumulative probability curves presented in figure 5.

Figure 5: Reliability curve of M versus \sqrt{t} (C.P. — cumulative probability)

In the same way, we can obtain the reliability curve of $M(t)$ for any reliability degree R (0.95, 0.99 or others).

These curves provide a statistical estimate of the water absorption process; moreover, they provide an analytical base for us to study the dispersion on degradation of mechanical properties of composite materials due to water absorption.

CONCLUSIONS

On the basis of the results obtained, the following conclusions can be made regarding the statistical analysis on the water absorption process of the glass/epoxy composites:

1. The statistical analysis of this paper is established on the specimens which possess the same volume fraction of the fiber but different laminated types. This kind of treatment will result in a statistical law in a more broad sense.
2. The statistical distributions of the moisture content well approximate the Normal Distribution on the nearly whole absorption process.
3. The statistical law of water absorption can be described as the classical Fick' law with addition to a statistical modification.
4. A reliability curve of the moisture content $M(t)$ is given which may be practically employed for the water absorption process of the glass/epoxy composites.

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